

Mathematical Analysis of a Prey-Predator Population Model with a Nonlinear Harvesting Rate Using New Homotopy Perturbation Method

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Abstract

This study discusses the application of the New Homotopy Perturbation Method in a prey-predator population model with a nonlinear harvesting rate. Using the novel approach, approximate analytical formulas for the populations of the prey and predator have been derived. The analytical solution is plotted against the numerical simulation, and found to make a good fit. Additionally, the effects of different parameters on the populations are also examined.

Keywords: Prey–Predator model; Harvesting Rate; New approach to Homotopy Perturbation Method; Numerical Simulation.

1. Introduction

A linear differential equation is a differential equation that is defined by a linear polynomial in the unknown function and its derivatives. A differential equation that is not linear is termed to be a nonlinear differential equation. While the exact solutions to some nonlinear differential equations are known, many of the critical ones in practical applications remain unsolved.

A crucial tool in mathematical ecology, the predator-prey model is a nonlinear mathematical model that helps us understand how populations interact in the natural world. A population is any group of individuals belonging to the same species that reside in a comparable geographic area. Preys are animals that are killed and consumed by other creatures, while predators are animals that preys on and consumes other creatures. Predictions are made by building mathematical formulas and models on the basis of observations and experimentation.

A non-linear differential equation can be analytically approximated using a variety of asymptotic methods[2], including the Homotopy Analysis Method[3, 4], Akbari-Ganji's Method [5-7], Adomian

Decomposition Method [8,9], Homotopy Perturbation Method[10], and others.

Differential equations with nonlinearities can be solved to get approximate solutions using the New Homotopy Perturbation Method[11 - 27]. This study's primary objective is to use the NHPM to estimate a solution for a previously developed prey-predator population model with a nonlinear harvesting rate[1].

2. Mathematical Formulation of the Problem

The proposed prey-predator model[1] is,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = xr \left(1 - \frac{x}{k}\right) - axy - \alpha x^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = caxy - dy - \beta y^3 \quad (2)$$

with initial conditions,

$$t = 0, \quad x(0) = x_0 \quad \& \quad y(0) = y_0 \quad (3)$$

where the description for the parameters are,

- x represents the size of prey population.
- y represents the size of predator population.
- a represents the rate of predation.
- c represents the factor of the efficiency of predation.
- d represents the death rate of predators.
- r represents the maximum specific growth rate of the prey.
- k represents the environmental carrying capacity.

3. Approximate analytical solution of equations (1) to (3) using New approach to Homotopy Perturbation Method

Construct the Homotopy for equations (1) and (2) as follows:

$$(1 - p) \left[\frac{dx}{dt} - xr \left(1 - \frac{x_0}{k}\right) + axy + \alpha x_0 x \right] + p \left[\frac{dx}{dt} - xr \left(1 - \frac{x}{k}\right) + axy + \alpha x^2 \right] = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$(1 - p) \left[\frac{dy}{dt} - cax_0 y + dy + \beta y_0^2 y \right] + p \left[\frac{dy}{dt} - caxy + dy + \beta y^3 \right] = 0 \quad (5)$$

Solving the above equations using initial conditions, we get

$$x(t) = x_0 e^{\frac{-ay_0 k e^{(cax_0 - d - \beta y_0^2)t - ((\alpha x_0 - r)k + x_0 r)(cax_0 - d - \beta y_0^2)t + ak y_0}}{k(cax_0 - d - \beta y_0^2)}} \quad (6)$$

$$y(t) = y_0 e^{(cax_0 - d - \beta y_0^2)t} \quad (7)$$

4. Graphical Representation of Prey and Predator Populations:

Fig 1. Plot of prey population for parameter values $d = 0.2$, $r = 0.1$, $k = 0.5$, $c = 1.8$, $a = 0.5$, $\alpha = 0.25$, $\beta = 0.1$, $x_0 = 10$, $y_0 = 10$. The solid black line denotes the analytical solution and the black dash line represents the numerical simulation.

Fig(2a) Plot of PREY population (x) obtained by varying parameter a and fixing all other parameter values as $d = 0.2$, $r = 0.1$, $k = 0.5$, $c = 1.8$, $\alpha = 0.25$, $\beta = 0.1$, $x_0 = 3$, $y_0 = 10$.

Fig(2b) Plot of PREY population (x) obtained by varying parameter d and fixing other parameter values as $a = 0.5$, $r = 0.1$, $k = 0.5$, $c = 1.8$, $\alpha = 0.25$, $\beta = 0.1$, $x_0 = 2$, $y_0 = 6$.

Fig(2c) Plot of PREY population (x) obtained by varying parameter r and fixing all other parameter values as $a = 0.5$, $c = 1.8$, $k = 0.5$, $d = 0.2$, $\alpha = 0.25$, $\beta = 0.1$, $x_0 = 2$, $y_0 = 10$.

Fig(2d) Plot of PREY population (x) obtained by varying parameter c and fixing all other parameter values as $a = 0.5$, $r = 0.1$, $k = 0.5$, $d = 0.2$, $\alpha = 0.25$, $\beta = 0.1$, $x_0 = 2$, $y_0 = 7$.

Fig(3a) Plot of PREDATOR population (y) obtained by varying parameter d and fixing all other parameter values as $a = 0.5$, $r = 0.1$, $k = 0.5$, $c = 1.8$, $\alpha = 0.25$, $\beta = 0.1$, $x_0 = 10$, $y_0 = 10$.

Fig(3b) Plot of PREDATOR population (y) obtained by varying parameter c and fixing all other parameter values as $a = 0.5$, $r = 0.1$, $k = 0.5$, $d = 0.2$, $\alpha = 0.25$, $\beta = 0.1$, $x_0 = 10$, $y_0 = 10$.

Fig(3c) Plot of PREDATOR population (y) obtained by varying parameter a and fixing all other parameter values as $c = 1.8$, $r = 0.1$, $k = 0.5$, $d = 0.2$, $\alpha = 0.25$, $\beta = 0.1$, $x_0 = 2$, $y_0 = 6$.

5. Results and discussion

Equations (6) and (7) denote simple analytical expressions that approximate the prey and predator populations in the Predator-Prey model, which is represented by equations (1) through (3). Figure 1 shows that there is a good agreement between the numerical solutions achieved using MATLAB and the analytical formulas that were developed for the Predator - Prey model.

The prey population (fig. 2a) falls as the rate of predation increases, indicating a negative relationship between the parameter 'a' and the prey population. The prey population (fig. 2b) rises in tandem with an increase in the predator mortality rate (d), suggesting that parameter 'd' positively affects the prey population. The prey population (fig. 2c) increases as 'r', the maximum specific growth rate of the prey, drops, suggesting that 'r' has a negative effect on the prey population. The prey population (fig. 2d) grows when the parameter 'c', the factor of the effectiveness of predation, drops, suggesting that the parameter 'c' has a negative effect on the prey population. The predator population (fig. 3a) reduces when the parameter 'd' rises, indicating that the parameter 'd' has an adverse effect on the predator population. The drop in the predator population (fig. 3b) coincides with a decrease in parameter 'c', the efficiency of predation factor. This suggests that 'c' has a favorable effect on the predator population. The fact that the predator population in fig. (3c) reduces as the rate of predation decreases due to parameter 'a' indicates that the parameter has a beneficial effect on the predator population.

6. Conclusion

In this work, we have discussed the effects of non-linear harvesting in a predator-prey model in which both the species are harvested. The approximate analytical solution for the considered prey-predator model with nonlinear harvesting rate was derived using the New approach to Homotopy Perturbation Method. The analytical results obtained will help researchers to better understand the model and to interpret the effects of the different parameters on the population.

Appendix: A

MATLAB program to find the numerical solution of eqns. (1) to (3)

```
function graphmain3
options= odeset('RelTol', 1e-6, 'Stats', 'on');
%initial conditions
Xo = [10;10];
Tspan = [0 1];
Tic
[t , X] =ode45 (@TestFunction, tspan, Xo, options);
toc
figure
hold on
plot (t, X( : , 1), '-')
plot (t, X( : , 2), '-')
legend ('x1', 'x2')
ylabel('X')
xlabel('t')
return
function [dx_dt] = TestFunction(~, x)
d = 0.2; r = 0.1; k = 0.5; c = 1.8 ;a = 0.5;  $\alpha$  = 0.25;  $\beta$  = 0.1;
dx_dt(1) = x(1) * r *  $\left(1 - \frac{x(1)}{k}\right)$  - a*x(1)*x(2) -  $\alpha$ *x(1)^2;
dx_dt(2) = c*a*x(1)*x(2) - d*x(2) -  $\beta$ *x(2)^3;
dx_dt = dx_dt';
return
```

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